

SIMULATION OF VERY UNBALANCED TEXTILE FORMING

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SUMMARY: If geometrical methods used for woven composite forming are fast and efficient, they do not account for mechanical behaviour of the fabric and of static boundary conditions. The goal of this work is to show the importance of those two points in the case of the forming of a very unbalanced reinforcement. The simulation is made using simplified finite elements based on the tensile deformation energy of the yarns. The results of the analysis are compared to an experimental forming. The result of the drawing process is very dependent of the mechanical behaviour of the fabric.

KEYWORDS: Fabric, Forming, Finite elements, Unbalanced fabric, Fabric mechanical behaviour

INTRODUCTION

Fibre fabrics are among the most efficient reinforcements for thin composite materials. The use of glass, carbon or aramid fibres is much increasing in aeronautic and automotive industries. Complex shapes can be obtained by deformation of the fabrics on a given surface before resin injection (R.T.M. process [1-3]) or resin polymerisation [4]. Conception of such components is delicate. The forming modes of fabrics are specific to this material and related to its woven constitution. It is necessary to know if the requested shape is reachable by forming the fibre fabric and secondly, where are the reinforcement directions after forming. In this goal, fishnet algorithms, assume inextensive yarns and that the rotation between warp and weft directions is free. They are very fast and efficient especially for the simulation of hand operated draping [5-8]. Nevertheless in the case of forming with punch and die the static boundary conditions (loads on the blank holder for instance) may be very important. In addition the physical properties of the fabric, i.e. the material for the warp and the weft yarns, and the type of weaving should be included in the analysis. An objective of the proposed paper is to show that the mechanical properties of the fabric can be very important for the result of the shaping process. The mechanical behaviour of dry fabrics such as used in the forming stage of the R.T.M. process depends on the yarn behaviour and on the weave pattern, leading to interactions between warp and weft directions and non linear behaviour. These geometrical non-

linearities due to changes in yarn crimp under tension have been studied from biaxial tests on cross-shaped specimens [9][10]. The fabric studied in the present paper is very unbalanced. The rigidity in warp direction is much larger than in the weft direction. An experimental forming test will be presented that shows the very large effect of the non-symmetry of the fabric behaviour on the forming result. This forming process is simulated, within an explicit dynamic approach, using simplified finite elements in which the interior load vectors are calculated from the tensile energy of each yarn [11]. This approach gives a computed fabric shape after forming in good agreement with the experimental result. The test performed experimentally and simulated clearly shows that it is necessary in this case to use a method that accounts for the fabric mechanical behaviour and for the boundary condition to obtain a good simulation result.

A SIMPLIFIED MECHANICAL APPROACH FOR THE FABRIC FORMING SIMULATION

The diameter of fibres used in yarns of textile reinforcement is very small (5 to 7 μm for carbon and 5 to 25 μm for glass) regarding their length. Consequently these fibres can only be submitted to a tensile stress in fibre direction \mathbf{h}_1 . The yarns that are used classically for R.T.M. preforms are simply juxtaposed (untwisted). This permits a relative sliding of the fibres in case of a yarn curvature and the stress state in the yarn can be assumed to be in form :

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \sigma^{11} \mathbf{h}_1 \otimes \mathbf{h}_1 + \sigma^{22} \mathbf{h}_2 \otimes \mathbf{h}_2 \quad \text{Eqn. 2}$$

\mathbf{h}_1 and \mathbf{h}_2 are unit vectors in warp and weft yarn directions. $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor. The tensor tensor is defined as :

$$\mathbf{T} = T^{11} \mathbf{h}_1 \otimes \mathbf{h}_1 + T^{22} \mathbf{h}_2 \otimes \mathbf{h}_2 \quad \text{Eqn. 3}$$

with

$$T^{11} = \int_{A_1} \sigma^{11} dS \quad , \quad T^{22} = \int_{A_2} \sigma^{22} dS \quad , \quad T^{11} \geq 0 \quad , \quad T^{22} \geq 0 \quad \text{Eqn. 4}$$

Fig 1. Fibres and yarns

Fig 2. Woven yarns

For a woven domain made of n elementary woven cells, the dynamic equation can be written in the following form:

$$\sum_{p=1}^{ncell} {}^p \varepsilon_{11}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) {}^p T^{11} {}^p L_1 + {}^p \varepsilon_{22}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) {}^p T^{22} {}^p L_2 - T_{ext}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) = \int_{\Omega} \rho u \boldsymbol{\eta} dV \quad \text{Eqn. 5}$$

$$\forall \boldsymbol{\eta} / \boldsymbol{\eta} = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_u$$

$T_{ext}(\boldsymbol{\eta})$ is the virtual work of the exterior loads:

$$T_{ext}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot \boldsymbol{\eta} dV - \int_{\Gamma_t} \mathbf{t} \cdot \boldsymbol{\eta} dS \quad \text{Eqn. 6}$$

3D surface finite element are defined on this approach. They are made of $ncell^e$ elementary cells. Warp and weft directions are the natural directions of the element. The finite element presented (Figure 3) is a three-node triangle. This element is not based on continuum mechanics where the behaviour relating the stress and the strain would correspond to the behaviour of a fibre fabric. It is a discreet element where the deformation energy of each elementary woven cell is added in the deformation energy of the element. The relations within an elementary woven cell between the two tensions (T^{11} , T^{22}) and the two strains (E_{11} , E_{22}) give the behaviour of this elementary woven cell as studied and modelled in [9],[11]. This is closer to the physics of the fabric and allows introducing enhanced models for any kind of fabric. The other advantage is the simplicity of the components of the interior nodal loads of the element as it will be shown later.

Fig. 3. Finite Element composed of woven elementary cells

The material coordinates ξ_1 , ξ_2 are measured in the warp and weft yarn directions. They define initial material covariant vectors \mathbf{g}_{10} , \mathbf{g}_{20} , the current material covariant vectors \mathbf{g}_1 , \mathbf{g}_2 and the associated contravariant vectors. (α, β are index taking the value 1 or 2)

$$\mathbf{g}_{\alpha 0} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_0}{\partial \xi_\alpha} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{\partial N^i}{\partial \xi_\alpha} \mathbf{x}_0^i \quad \mathbf{g}_\alpha = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \xi_\alpha} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{\partial N^i}{\partial \xi_\alpha} \mathbf{x}^i \quad \mathbf{g}_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{g}^\beta = \delta_\alpha^\beta \quad \text{Eqn. 8}$$

Fabric forming is a quasi-static process. Nevertheless efficient numerical simulations of forming processes are based on explicit dynamic methods [11][12][13] where it is checked that the dynamic effects are small. In such an approach, the equilibrium equation is completed by acceleration terms. Accounting for the finite element approximation, Eqn. 5 can be extended to the equation of the motion for a fabric :

$$\sum_{p=1}^{n \text{ cell}} {}^p \varepsilon_{11}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) {}^p T^{11} {}^p L_1 + {}^p \varepsilon_{22}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) {}^p T^{22} {}^p L_2 - \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot \boldsymbol{\eta} dV - \int_{\Gamma_t} \mathbf{t} \cdot \boldsymbol{\eta} dA = \int_{\Omega} \rho \ddot{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \boldsymbol{\eta} dV$$

$$\nabla \boldsymbol{\eta} / \boldsymbol{\eta} = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_u \quad \text{Eqn. 9}$$

where $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}$ is the acceleration corresponding to the displacement \mathbf{u} and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\boldsymbol{\eta})$ is the gradient tensor in the virtual displacement $\boldsymbol{\eta}$. Introducing some damping, the discretised equation of the motion is

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_n + \mathbf{C} \dot{\mathbf{u}}_n = \mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}} - \mathbf{F}_{\text{int}} \quad \text{Eqn. 10}$$

\mathbf{M} and \mathbf{C} are the mass and damping matrices, $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_n$ and $\dot{\mathbf{u}}_n$ are the nodal accelerations and velocities, \mathbf{F}_{ext} and \mathbf{F}_{int} are the nodal external and interior loads. Equations 10 are integrated in time using an explicit scheme which is based on the use of a diagonal mass matrix. Consequently, there is no need to solve a system of equations and the method is very effective. On a time step Δt^i , from t^i to t^{i+1} , the central difference scheme gets the solution \mathbf{u}_n^{i+1} from \mathbf{u}_n^i by :

$$\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_n^{i+1} = \mathbf{M}_D^{-1} \left(\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}^i - \mathbf{F}_{\text{int}}^i - \mathbf{C} \dot{\mathbf{u}}_n^i \right) \quad \text{Eqn. 11}$$

where \mathbf{M}_D is a diagonal matrix calculated from the mass matrix [14].

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}_n^{i+1/2} = \dot{\mathbf{u}}_n^{i-1/2} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\Delta t^{i-1} + \Delta t^i \right) \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_n^{i+1} \quad \text{Eqn. 12}$$

$$\mathbf{u}_n^{i+1} = \mathbf{u}_n^i + \dot{\mathbf{u}}_n^{i+1/2} \Delta t^i \quad \text{Eqn. 13}$$

The time step size has to insure the stability condition of the integration scheme accounting for the element size and the material data [12][15]. Without introducing significant error in equation 12 $\dot{\mathbf{u}}_n^i$ can be substituted by $\dot{\mathbf{u}}_n^{i-1/2}$. The term which is specific to the studied finite element made of fabric is the nodal interior load \mathbf{F}_{int} .

Accounting for the simplified form 9 of the equation of the motion and denoting \mathbf{A}_{elt}

the assemblage operator on the elements of the fabric blank, $\mathbf{F}_{int} = \mathbf{A}_{elt} \mathbf{F}_{int}^e$

$$\sum_{p=1}^{n_{cell}^e} {}^p \varepsilon_{11}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) {}^p T^{11} {}^p L_1 + {}^p \varepsilon_{22}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) {}^p T^{22} {}^p L_2 = \sum_{p=1}^{n_{cell}^e} (\eta_n^e)_s (\mathbf{F}_{int}^e)_s \quad \text{Eqn. 14}$$

where the superscript e denotes that the quantity is relative to element e, and where the subscript s denotes the component s of an unicum column matrix.

The virtual strains are interpolated from the virtual displacements :

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta} \mathbf{h}^{\alpha 0} \otimes \mathbf{h}^{\beta 0} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\beta} \mathbf{g}^{\alpha 0} \otimes \mathbf{g}^{\beta 0} \quad \text{Eqn. 15}$$

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\alpha}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) = \varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) \left\| \mathbf{g}_{\alpha 0} \right\|^2 = \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}}{\partial \xi_\alpha} \cdot \mathbf{g}_{\alpha 0} = \bar{\mathbf{B}}_{\alpha as} \eta_s^e \quad \text{Eqn. 16}$$

where the components of the strain interpolation matrix are :

$$\bar{\mathbf{B}}_{\alpha as} = \frac{\partial N^k}{\partial \xi_\alpha} (\mathbf{g}_{\alpha 0})_m \text{ with } k = \text{integer} \left(\frac{s+2}{3} \right), \quad m = s-3(k+1) \quad \text{Eqn. 17}$$

consequently

$$\left(\mathbf{F}_{int}^e \right)_s = \sum_{p=1}^{n_{cell}^e} \bar{\mathbf{B}}_{11s} \left\| \mathbf{g}_{10} \right\|^{-2} {}^p T^{11} {}^p L_{0_1} + \bar{\mathbf{B}}_{22s} \left\| \mathbf{g}_{20} \right\|^{-2} {}^p T^{22} {}^p L_{0_2} \quad \text{Eqn. 18}$$

Accounting for the linearity of the interpolation functions and denoting N_c and N_t the cell numbers in warp and weft directions

$$\left(\mathbf{F}_{int}^e \right)_s = \frac{N_c N_t}{2} \left(\bar{\mathbf{B}}_{11s} L_{0_1} T^{11} \left\| \mathbf{g}_{10} \right\|^{-2} + \bar{\mathbf{B}}_{22s} L_{0_2} T^{22} \left\| \mathbf{g}_{20} \right\|^{-2} \right) \quad \text{Eqn. 19}$$

This expression of the nodal interior loads is very simple and only needs the calculation of the tensions T^{11} and T^{22} from the strain state which is done following experimental or numerical investigations presented in [9-11]. This results in a good numerical efficiency.

EXPERIMENTS AND SIMULATION

The tool geometry (including the blank-holder) is shown in Figure 4. A 6 kg ring was used as a blank-holder, to avoid wrinkles. Press mouldings were held with a hemispherical punch-die couple, mounted on a classical 25kN-Instron machine.

The tests were performed in the composites laboratory of the School of MMMEM at the University of Nottingham.

The preforms were impregnated with a translucent polyester resin after forming to freeze their movements. A grid of 10mmx10mm elements was drawn on the fabric prior to forming to measure the fibre angle variations and the elongations in each direction.

Fig. 4 Tool geometry

The fabric used for this experiment is a 2x2 nylon twill, used in automotive parts as a reinforcement in elastomer composites. Each tow contains approximately 40 fibres. The weft tows have a double crimped path: the normal weaving crimp and their own waviness due to their texturizing (Figure 5). This strong difference between warp and weft tows results in a very unbalanced mechanical behaviour, as shown in Figure 6. The densities of yarns are 2.8 both in warp and weft directions. The surface density is 3.47 gsm. Uni-axial traction tests exhibit a non-linear behaviour. But, for a given range of elongation, it is possible to define an equivalent linear modulus in each direction (given in Table 1). The stiffness modulus in warp direction is about 50 N/yarn and those in weft direction is 0.2 N/yarn.

Fig. 5 Weft and warp yarns

Fig. 6. Warp and weft tensile behaviour

The shape obtained after forming is shown on figure 7. At the top of the hemisphere, the weft elongation is maximum, and the warp elongation remains very low. Thus, the ratio reaches 1/1.8, which is very specific to this unbalanced fabric. In the meantime, warp and weft deformed edges of the blank exhibit strong differences. The shear angle has been measured on one quadrant by an optical method in use at the University of Nottingham. The highest shear angle is 39°, at the base of the hemisphere. It is not symmetrical, this angle is maximum at the approximate meridian direction $\Phi = 30^\circ$, from the warp direction (so-called 0° direction). On a balanced fabric, due to the symmetry, the maximum shear angle direction is located at $\Phi = 45^\circ$ [16-18].

Fig. 7 Shape after forming. Experiment and simulation

Fig. 8 Angles between warp and weft yarns after forming

The shape after forming given by a simulation using the simplified elements shown on figure 7 and compared to the experimental shape described by the computation. The main feature is different in the warp and weft directions. The shape is horizontal on Figure 9. The stretching in the central part due to the blank holder. The displacements on the horizontal axis are very small. On the vertical direction is small and consequently the warp and weft yarns exhibit large displacements towards the center.

weft yarns (N/yarn)

However the numerical simulation don't lead to any wrinkle while they are important in practice. The lack of in-plane shear stiffness leads to a solution without instabilities. Nevertheless, if the finite element computation does not describe the wrinkles, it permits to determine their appearance. Actually, the warp weft angle variations (figure 8) permit to determine the zones where this angle is larger to the limit angle of the fabric. This angle is about 35° for the fabric under consideration. It is largely exceeded in the zone where wrinkles occur. Figure 8 show (and that is in agreement with experiment) that the shearing zones are not at 45° as it is the case for a balanced fabric [16-17]. Tensions in the yarns are computed. They are shown figure 9 for the weft direction. Their knowledge permit to limit the blank-holder force in order to avoid fabric tearing. In the studied case the risk concerns the weft direction where the axial strain is 0.87 while the limite is 1.1.

CONCLUSION

This work shows that the mechanical behaviour of the fabric can be important in a forming process. In this case a mechanical approach is necessary to account for this aspect. The static boundary conditions i.e. the loads on the tools can also be very important for the final result of forming. An hemispherical forming experiment performed on a very unbalanced fabric has shown that the result is highly non-symmetric. This result cannot be obtained by classical geometric draping algorithms. A simplified finite element based on the tension energy of each yarn has been used with an explicit dynamic approach. The computed shape after forming is in correct agreement with the experimental one. The wrinkles are not modelled at present. With this in mind elements with in plane shear and bending stiffness are now being developed.

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REFERENCES

1. Carronnier D. and Gay D. "Approche intégrée du RTM", *Revue des composites et des matériaux avancés*, 1996, Vol.6.
2. Gauvin, R., Trochu, F., Lemenn, Y., and Diallo, L. "Permeability measurement and flow simulation through fiber reinforcement", *Polymer Composites*, 1996, Vol.17, pp. 34-42
3. Potter, K.D., The early history of the resin transfert moulding for aerospace applications, *Composites A*, 30, 1999, 757-765

4. Wang, J., Paton, R., and Paye, J.R.. "The draping of woven fabric preforms and prepregs for production of polymer composite components", *Composites A*. 1999, Vol. 30, pp.757-765
5. Mark, C. and Taylor H. M. The fitting of woven cloth to surfaces. *Journal of Textile Institute*, 1956, Vol. 47, pp. 477-488
6. Van Der Ween, F., "Algorithms for draping fabrics on doubly curved surfaces", *Int. Journal of Numerical Method in Engineering*, Vol. 31, 1991, p. 1414-1426
7. Long, A.C. and Rudd C.D., A simulation of reinforcement deformation during the production of preform for liquid moulding processes. *I. Mech. E. J. Eng. Manuf.*, 208, 1994, 269-278
8. Bickerton, S., Simacek, P., Guglielmi, S.E. And Advani, S.G. "Investigation of draping and its effects on the mold filling process during manufacturing of a compound curved composite part." *Composite Part A*, 1997, Vol. 28, pp.801-816
9. Buet K., Boisse Ph., "Experimental analysis and models for biaxial mechanical behaviour of composite woven reinforcements", *Experimental Mechanics*, 41, 3,260-269, 2001
10. P. Boisse, K. Buet, A. Gasser, J. Launay, Meso-macro mechanical behaviour of textile reinforcements of thin composites, *Composites Sci. and Technology*, 2001 , 61-3:395-401
11. Boisse, P., A. Gasser, and G. Hivet, Analyses of fabric behaviour : determination of the biaxial tension-strain surfaces and their use in forming simulations. *Composites Part A*. 32-10 (2001) 1395-1414
12. Belytschko, T., An overview of semidiscretisation and time integration procedures, *Computation methods for transient analysis*, ed. T. Belytschko & T.J.R.Hughes, Elsevier Science, 1983, 1-65
13. Hughes, T. J. H., Belytschko, T., A precis of developments in computational methods for transient analysis, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 50, 1983, 1033-1041
14. Crisfield, M.A., *Non-linear finite element analysis of solids and structures*, Wiley, 2, 1997
14. Zienkiewicz O. and Taylor R., *The finite element method*, 1, McGrawHill, 1989
15. Hughes, T. J. H., *The finite element method*, Prentice Hall, 1987
16. Aubourg, N. Mion, D., Etude de la Modélisation de l'emboutissage d'un tissu de fibres de verre. *Report PSA/Ecole Polytechnique*, 1989 (in french)
17. Ye, L. and H.R. Daghyani, Characteristics of woven fibre fabric reinforced composites in forming process. *Composites Part A*. 28A (1997) 869-874.
18. Rudd, C.D., M.R. Turner, A.C. Long, and V. Middleton, Tow placement studies for liquid composite moulding. *Composites Part A*. 30-9 (1999) 1105-1121